

Human Rights Education : The Teachers Rights and Responsibilities

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The Role of teacher is progressively being broadened from that the expert who imparts knowledge to one that includes a mentor or guide, one who extends students deep understandings. In the establishment of human rights culture the role of teachers is undoubtedly illustrious. Teachers occupy a crucial position in the educational process and substantially influence the shaping of the future. The purpose of this paper is to analyze the teachers rights and responsibilities in schools/ universities in the Human Rights Education (HRE).

Human Rights :

Born out the atrocities and enormous loss of life during World war-II, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights was created by the United Nations (UN)

Rights and Responsibilities:

According to Kid's Health; all human have basic rights.

- i) The right to life & liberty
- ii) The right to work & to own property
- iii) The right to education (According to Article-26)
- iv) The right to vote, to have justice & to petition.
- v) Right to hold public office.
- vi) Freedom of thought and speech as well as freedom of the press.

Human Right Education: Indian Scenario :

HRE is important because it can prevent violation of human rights, promote assertion of human rights and human rights is an essential part of social studies curriculum. National policy on Education underlines the importance of value

Education ? Human Right is not treated as separate subject in the curricula NCERT. UGC appointed Sikri Committee in 1980- promoting HRE in India.

Teacher Rights :

The process of teaching & learning take place in an environment in which the rights to teachers & students are constantly being balanced against the rights and responsibilities of school officials to maintain a safe, caring and orderly environment (Webb, 2000). Teachers also have rights. They are

- i) Rights under the Amendments.
- ii) Academic Freedom
- iii) Freedom of Expression.
- iv) Teacher Rights in Assertive Discipline.
- v) Freedom of Association
- vi) Freedom of Religion.
- vii) Professional Freedom.
- viii) Privacy Rights
- ix) Age
- x) Pregnancy.

Teachers Responsibilities :

The responsibilities of teachers and rights of students directly affect each other. Therefore teachers know his responsibilities. The responsibilities are –

- i) Responsibilities towards profession
- ii) Responsibilities towards Children/ Students.
- iii) Responsibilities towards parents.
- iv) Responsibilities towards higher authority.
- v) Responsibilities towards HRE.

Conditions ensuring effective role of teachers :

Teacher Training : In order that teachers effectively inculcate human rights in students, we need to focus on Teacher Education (T.E.)

- i) NCTE - Shall ensure inclusion of HR in the curriculum of diploma, bachelor and masters programmes in Education.
- ii) NCF- 2005 states that in service training can play a significant role.
 - * Syllabus & Textbook:- Teachers should forward their constructive suggestions for making syllabus & textbook.
 - * Experience Sharing: - Organizations of teachers can also conduct interactive experiences sharing sessions.

Teachers need to be motivated to have additional qualification in human rights through incentives.

Teacher plays an important role such as sculptor, entertainer, the coach, parent, guide, coordinator & he has major responsibility to make new generations (students) as good citizens having, good knowledge & skills, values, attitudes & behavior & Action.

So for effective human right teaching, the school/ Universities shall take serious efforts in empowering teachers with information, planning, management & instructions because “The destiny of India is being shaped in her classroom.”

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